

FAIR PRINCIPLES TRAINING SCHOOL

Over the past few months, the HemaFAIR project (in collaboration with HELIOS COST Action) took a major leap forward in building capacity for FAIR data management through our very first Training School on FAIR Principles.

Held in Larnaca, Cyprus, this hands-on event brought together researchers, data stewards, and project managers from across our consortium and beyond. Participants moved beyond theory and gained practical experience applying FAIR principles to real-world data challenges – from metadata standards and data sharing to registries and data reuse.

CHECK OUT THE NEXT PAGE FOR SOME GREAT MOMENTS FROM THE EVENT!

FOSTERING F.A.I.R DATA
AND STANDARDS IN RARE
HEMATOLOGICAL
DISEASES

WANT TO HEAR WHAT OUR COORDINATOR, TRAINERS, AND PARTICIPANTS HAD TO SAY? HEAD OVER TO OUR LINKEDIN PAGE TO WATCH THE HIGHLIGHTS!

OUR LATEST DELIVERABLES

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Training Bottom-up Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101159589.

Fostering F.A.I.R. Data and Standards
in Rare Hematological Diseases

Deliverable 9.1

Methodology for identifying funding opportunities in RD/RHD with a pilot list of opportunities

Project Acronym	HemaFAIR
Grant Agreement No.	101159589
Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02-01
Start date	1 st of July, 2024
Project duration	36 months

Disclaimer

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Training Program

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The last quarter was a busy one for the HemaFAIR team — it was a season of submissions! We've wrapped up and submitted key project deliverables, including:

D7.1 Training programme description
D 9.1 Methodology document for identifying suitable research and funding opportunities in RD/RHD and biomedical informatics

You can find these and all our public outputs on our Zenodo page:

zenodo

SHORT-TERM STAFF EXCHANGES TO ITALY AND THE NETHERLANDS!

Our short-term staff exchanges are in full swing, helping us build expertise across borders and bring valuable knowledge back to Cyprus.

TO THE NETHERLANDS!

Stella Tamana from CING traveled to Amsterdam and Leiden to dive deep into FAIRification practices. From exploring tools to refining clinical questions for our use case, Stella's visit was all about hands-on learning – and now she's bringing that knowledge home to strengthen our work locally.

TO ITALY!

Coralea Stephanou visited our expert partners in Bari for a collaboration focused on the ethical side of innovation. Together, they're exploring how AI intersects with ethics, legal, and social issues (ELSI) in rare disease research. The outcome? A systematic review that will guide future work in this important space.

LECTURE SERIES: A GREAT SESSION ON PROJECT MANAGEMENT IN EU PROJECTS

We had an exciting session on project management!

We were thrilled to welcome Kimberley Kenter, an experienced project manager with hands-on expertise coordinating MSCA Doctoral Networks.

Kimberley guided us through the ins and outs of pre- and post-award management, sharing practical tips, real-life challenges, and best practices for running successful EU-funded projects.

**LECTURE
SERIES #10**

JULY 21, 2025
2PM-3PM (EEST)

KIMBERLEY RENTNER
GRANT ADVISOR, PROJECT
MANAGER
AMSTERDAM UNIVERSITY
MEDICAL CENTER

MARIE CURIE DOCTORAL NETWORKS
ONLINE ON MICROSOFT TEAMS APP

Marie
Skłodowska-
Curie Actions

WHAT'S NEXT FOR HEMAFAIR?

ON THE HORIZON

TECHNICAL UPDATES

Patient reported outcomes

After careful review, we've selected two tools to capture patient-reported outcomes for our research:

- SF-36 – A widely used generic tool to assess overall health-related quality of life across different conditions
- TransQoL – A disease-specific tool designed for patients with transfusion-dependent thalassemia

Next up: we'll be integrating both tools into our patient registry using the REDCap platform – bringing us one step closer to a more patient-centred, data-driven research approach!

FAIRification of Patient Registries

Our team at CING is working closely with FAIR experts across the consortium to define the requirements for our research use case. This involves FAIRifying one local platform – the Cyprus Haemoglobinopathy Patient Registry – and one international platform – INHERENT.

This collaboration will help ensure both platforms meet FAIR standards and support broader data sharing and reuse.

